
Utilización de aprendizaje automático para predecir problemas cardíacos a partir de datos de dispositivos portátiles

Utilizing Machine Learning to Predict Cardiac Issues from Wearable Device Data

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RESUMEN. Los problemas cardíacos son una de las principales causas de mortalidad en el mundo, con aproximadamente 17 millones de muertes cada año. La detección temprana de estas enfermedades es esencial para reducir la mortalidad y mejorar la calidad de vida de la población. El objetivo de este estudio fue desarrollar un sistema predictivo que, a partir de datos obtenidos de dispositivos portátiles, específicamente relojes inteligentes, permita identificar la probabilidad de aparición de problemas cardíacos. Para ello, se emplearon datos públicos procedentes de la plataforma Google Fit y de un conjunto de datos abierto disponible en Kaggle. El proceso metodológico incluyó técnicas de preprocesamiento como imputación de valores faltantes, normalización de datos y codificación de variables categóricas. Se entrenaron y evaluaron cuatro algoritmos de aprendizaje automático: Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, Decision Tree y Random Forest. El desempeño de los modelos se evaluó mediante métricas de precisión, recall, F1-score y área bajo la curva (AUC). Los resultados mostraron que los algoritmos Random Forest y SVM obtuvieron los mejores desempeños, alcanzando un F1-score superior al 90% y una AUC máxima del 93%, lo que evidencia su capacidad predictiva para la identificación temprana de problemas cardíacos. En conclusión, este trabajo demuestra que la combinación de datos obtenidos de dispositivos portátiles con algoritmos de aprendizaje automático ofrece una herramienta confiable y accesible para la detección temprana y la prevención de enfermedades cardíacas, contribuyendo así al fortalecimiento de la medicina preventiva.

Palabras clave. Salud cardíaca, aprendizaje automático, dispositivos portátiles, modelado predictivo

ABSTRACT. Cardiac problems are one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately 17 million deaths each year. Early detection of these conditions is essential to reduce mortality rates and improve the population's quality of life. The objective of this study was to develop a predictive system that, using data obtained from wearable devices, specifically smartwatches, can identify the likelihood of cardiac problems. Publicly available data were collected from the Google Fit platform and an open dataset from Kaggle. The methodology included preprocessing techniques such as imputing missing values, normalizing data, and encoding categorical variables. Four machine learning algorithms were trained and evaluated: Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. The performance of the models was assessed using accuracy, recall, F1-score, and area under the curve (AUC). The results showed that the Random Forest and SVM algorithms achieved the best performances, reaching an F1-score above 90% and a maximum AUC of 93%, demonstrating strong predictive capability for the early identification of cardiac problems. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that combining data from wearable devices with machine learning algorithms provides a reliable and accessible tool for the early detection and prevention of cardiac diseases, thereby contributing to the advancement of preventive medicine.

Keywords. Cardiac Health, Machine Learning, Wearable Devices, Predictive Modelling

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1. Introducción

Healthcare 4.0, the current stage, integrates Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) to enable real-time data analysis from wearable devices synchronized with smartphones via network protocols like ZWave, Bluetooth, 3G, ZigBee, and 4G [1]. The widespread prevalence of smartphones has made them nearly ubiquitous in society [2]. Wearable devices have similarly gained popularity, evolving from fashion items to tools equipped with sensors for data collection. These devices measure steps, heart rate, productivity, location, and sleep patterns, fostering self-assessment capability among users.

Wearable devices have proven to be practical complementary diagnostic tools for managing long-term health conditions by providing continuous data for tracking patient progress. This ongoing monitoring reduces the reliance on more complex and costly medical interventions [3]. Furthermore, wearable technologies can gather and present preventive health data via smartphones before symptoms manifest, potentially replacing expensive medical devices and lowering healthcare costs by minimizing the need for corrective measures [4].

Current wearable devices, such as smartwatches and fitness bands, offer activity tracking and biometric sensing features like heart rate and body temperature monitoring. While these devices display various health metrics, there remains a question of whether their functions and services are appropriate and effective for health maintenance [5].

Sabry et al. comprehensively classify wearable devices within the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), categorising them into implantable, environmental, and stationary hospital devices [6]. These devices and user interactions generate vast amounts of data that can be analysed using Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to identify and understand health patterns.

This study significantly strides in developing a new wearable device based on machine learning (ML) algorithms to predict potential heart problems. The device will analyse data and present the results in a user-friendly mobile app, empowering individuals to monitor their heart health actively. To evaluate the performance of these ML algorithms, we employed a publicly available dataset here. The decision to focus on cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) as the object of

investigation was primarily motivated by the fact that, as stated by the World Health Organization [7] this specific condition indisputably dominates international mortality statistics, tragically claiming an impressive number of approximately 17.9 million lives annually. CVDs are a group of disorders of heart and blood vessels, including coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, rheumatic heart disease, and other conditions. More than four in every five CVD deaths are due to heart attacks and strokes, and one-third of these deaths occur prematurely in people under 70 years of age.

This paper addresses the following research question: Is it possible to develop an application that utilizes data collected from wearable devices to be analyzed by machine learning algorithms to predict cardiac problems? To address this question, the study is structured around developing and validating a prototype system that employs various ML algorithms, including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, and XGBoost, using a dataset from Kaggle.

The performance metrics of these algorithms in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and area under the curve (AUC) score are presented to demonstrate their effectiveness in predicting cardiac problems. The proposed solution involves developing an Application Programming Interface (API) for data storage and processing and a mobile application for data collection and user interaction. This system aims to achieve high accuracy and recall rates, providing a reliable tool for early detection of cardiac issues, thereby contributing to preventive medicine and improving overall health outcomes.

2. Background

2.1. Health Promotion

The global population has experienced increased longevity, with most expecting to live beyond 70 years. By 2030, one in six people worldwide will be 60 or older, with the elderly population growing from 1 billion in 2020 to 1.4 billion and doubling to 2.1 billion by 2050. The number of individuals aged 80 and above is projected to triple, reaching 426 million. This demographic shift is noteworthy in high-income nations such as Japan and low- and middle-income countries, which are anticipated to host two-thirds of the elderly population by 2050 [8] In Brazil, life expectancy for the elderly has increased from 69.1 years in 1940 to 76.6

years in 2019 [9]. Improving the quality of life and managing diseases effectively is crucial, with digital medicine playing a pivotal role [10]. Digital medicine focuses on early automated diagnosis, personalised therapies, individualised disease management, and revolutionising patient care [11]. Chronic diseases, particularly cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), represent significant public health challenges, significantly affecting morbidity and mortality among the elderly [12].

In addition, Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) such as CVDs, diabetes, chronic respiratory diseases, cancer, and autoimmune diseases are chronic and non-infectious, leading to over 36 million deaths annually, with 80% of these occurring in low and middle-income countries [8]. Thus, these diseases place a significant economic strain on health systems due to direct costs like medical consultations, hospitalizations, and medications and indirect costs such as productivity losses from premature mortality and disability [13]. Most premature deaths from NCDs are preventable through robust health systems and public policies targeting common risk factors, including tobacco use, unhealthy diets, physical inactivity, and harmful alcohol consumption [8]. Preventive measures against CVDs and other NCDs include quitting smoking, reducing alcohol intake, maintaining a balanced diet, engaging in regular physical activity, and sustaining a healthy weight [14].

2.2. Internet of Things (IoT) and Wearable Devices

The Internet of Things (IoT) integrates interconnected systems, people, and information resources with intelligent services managing real and virtual data [15]. With mainstream adoption evident in devices like smart speakers and connected cars, the IoT market is projected to reach 21.5 billion devices by 2025 [16]. The IoT infrastructure includes sensors, microcontrollers (e.g., Arduino, STM32, Intel Galileo, Raspberry Pi), and communication protocols (e.g., Bluetooth, ZigBee, LoRa Wan, GPRS), enabling data collection and task automation. These platforms also feature data management and analysis systems for task automation and informed decision-making [17].

Wearable devices, such as smartwatches and glasses, are equipped with sensors and wireless connectivity,

significantly enhancing the quality of life and health monitoring [18]. They generate and analyse personal health data using cloud, edge computing, and big data technologies to improve healthcare [19]. IoT and the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) enable real-time patient-provider communication, remote monitoring, early problem detection, and personalised treatments [20].

Combining wearable devices with machine learning advances healthcare by reducing monitoring costs and enhancing care through anomaly detection and instant alerts [21]. Data repositories like Kaggle and Mendeley test AI-based disease detection solutions, such as Google Brain's diabetic eye disease detection using deep learning and wearables for the visually impaired employing ultrasound for obstacle detection [22]. Google Fit, an open platform by Google Inc., exemplifies IoT applications in fitness tracking. As a free Android smartphone app, it uses sensors like accelerometers, gyroscopes, and GPS to monitor posture, movements, and various activities [23].

2.3. Machine Learning (ML) and Algorithm Selection

Machine Learning (ML) is an AI application that enables systems to learn and improve from experience, advancing rapidly due to increased data availability, affordable data storage, powerful computing resources, and advanced algorithms [24]. ML approaches involve training and decision phases: A model is learned from a dataset; during decision-making, the trained model predicts outputs for new inputs [25]. ML algorithms are categorized into supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement learning, each addressing different data processing needs [25], [26]. We have selected four ML algorithms to execute this work, as follows:

- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** A supervised learning method for classification and pattern recognition, mapping input vectors into a high-dimensional feature space to construct a linear decision surface [27].
- **XGBoost:** A scalable system for gradient boosting that combines multiple tree models to achieve high classification accuracy [28].

- **Decision Tree:** A supervised learning algorithm that employs a tree-like model for decision-making, illustrating decisions and their consequences [29].
- **Random Forest:** An ensemble learning method that uses multiple decision trees, each trained on random subsets of features, to enhance classification accuracy and reduce overfitting [30].

3. Experimental Design and Implementation

This section details the design and implementation of the experiments conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms in predicting cardiac problems using data collected from wearable devices. The experimental design focused on creating a robust framework to collect, preprocess, and analyze data from wearable devices to predict cardiac issues. The primary components of the design are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The primary components of experimental design.

3.1. Data Collection and Preprocessing

Data was collected using the Google Fit platform, which integrates with various smartwatches. This included (i) Heart rate (measured continuously), (ii) Steps (daily count), (iii) Sleep patterns (duration and quality), and (iv) Physical activity (type and duration). In addition, data related to the participant's cardiac medical history were collected. These data included aspects related to past cardiac events, current or past cardiac medication, or current CVD-related symptoms.

The preprocessing steps were crucial to preparing the data for model training; we have considered the following:

- **Missing Values:** Imputation techniques were used to handle missing data. Mean imputation was applied for numerical values, while mode imputation was used for categorical variables.
- **Normalization:** All numerical features were normalized to ensure they were on a comparable scale, which is essential for many machine learning algorithms.
- **Categorical Variables:** Categorical features were converted into numerical values using one-hot encoding.

3.2. Model Training and Validation

Each of the four selected algorithms was trained using preprocessed data. The training process involved:

- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** SVM was used for its effectiveness in high-dimensional spaces and its robustness to overfitting, particularly in cases where the number of dimensions exceeds the number of samples.
- **XGBoost:** Known for its scalability and efficiency, XGBoost handled large datasets and provided high accuracy through gradient boosting.
- **Decision Tree:** A decision tree was implemented for its simplicity and interpretability. It splits the data into subsets based on feature values, creating a tree-like model of decisions.
- **Random Forest:** An ensemble method that builds multiple decision trees and merges them to get a more accurate and stable prediction.

Cross-validation was performed to validate the models. The dataset was divided into k-folds (with $k = 5$), and the model was trained and validated k times, each time using a different fold as the validation set and the remaining folds as the training set. This process helped assess the model's performance and ensure it is generalized well to unseen data.

3.3. Metrics for Evaluating Machine Learning Algorithms

Accuracy, F1-score, and the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve are metrics used to evaluate the efficiency of ML models.

- **Accuracy:** Defined as the ratio of correctly predicted instances (true positives and true negatives) to the total instances.
- **F1-score:** A harmonic mean of precision (true positives divided by the sum of true and false positives) and recall (true positives divided by the sum of true positives and false negatives), balancing precision and recall.
- **ROC Curve:** A graphical plot illustrating the diagnostic ability of a binary classifier system, showing the trade-off between the true positive rate and the false positive rate at various threshold settings. These metrics provide a comprehensive understanding of the model's performance, helping to fine-tune parameters and compare different models effectively [31]

4. Implementation

The final implementation involved developing an application that integrates with wearable devices and uses the trained machine learning models to predict cardiac issues in real time.

4.1. Application Development

- **Frontend:** Developed using Flutter, providing a user-friendly data visualization and interaction interface
- **Backend:** Implemented in Java, the backend communicates with the wearable devices and the machine learning models. It uses RESTful APIs to handle data storage and prediction requests.

The application was tested with selected users to collect feedback and improve functionality. It was then deployed, enabling users to monitor their cardiac health and receive real-time alerts on potential issues.

5. Experimental Results

This section presents the results of experiments to evaluate the performance of machine learning algorithms used to predict cardiac problems based on data collected from wearable devices. The selected machine learning algorithms were analysed based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC metrics. Table 1 presents the performance metrics of the machine learning algorithms.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	ROC-AUC
SVM	91%	88%	96%	92%	90%
XGBoost	88%	88%	91%	89%	88%
Decision Tree	87%	88%	88%	88%	87%
Random Forest	91%	88%	97%	93%	93%

As shown in Table 1, the Random Forest and SVM algorithms demonstrated the highest scores across all metrics, indicating their effectiveness in identifying relevant instances and minimising false positives and negatives. The ROC-AUC metric, which provides an aggregate performance measure across all classification thresholds, further supports this finding. In this case, the Random Forest algorithm achieved the highest ROC-AUC score, underscoring its superior overall performance compared to the other algorithms. The Decision Tree and XGBoost models presented lower results, with values below 90% across all tested metrics except recall to XGBoost (91%).

6. Conclusion

This work aimed to create a solution to predict indicators of heart problems by collecting data through wearable devices. It looked for accuracy, precision, an F1-score above 80%, recall above 90%, and many true positives about true negatives. The Heart Failure Prediction database was selected because it is in the public domain and contains valuable variables for the study. In the pre-processing stage, the data was processed and separated into two parts: training and testing.

Regarding the chosen models, Vector Machine Support and Random Forest, the latter obtained the best overall metrics. The proposed solution was developed

through an application in Flutter that integrates an API developed in Java with the Spring Boot framework. The application developed managed to achieve the main objective of this work, thus managing to collect data and send it to predict indicators of heart problems through a machine learning model. Random Forest was chosen as the final model for the machine learning model. A small API was developed with only one service to be consumed by the Java Backend API, which was developed publicly. It is only a service for receiving data and returning results, not saving them.

Considering that the application is ready, the next step will be to test it with potential users and validate it with experts in the field. In future work, it is initially proposed to collect data with a group of people to generate a more varied database with data that is easier to collect by wearable devices (smartwatches).

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding the development and publication of this article.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS AND APPROVAL

- **Vinicius de Aquino Piai:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – Original Draft Preparation.
- **Raimundo C. G. Teive:** Data Curation, Validation, Formal Analysis.
- **Luis Augusto Silva:** Visualization, Supervision, Writing – Review and Editing.
- **Anita M. da Rocha Fernandes:** Supervision, Project Administration, Resources.

- **Wemerson D. Parreira:** Software, Validation, Investigation.
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All authors affirm that they have read and approved the final version of this article.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Bhattacharya, S. Tanwar, U. Bodkhe, S. Tyagi, and N. Kumar, “Bindaas: Block-chain-based deep-learning as-a-service in healthcare 4.0 applications,” *IEEE Trans Netw Sci Eng*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1242–1255, 2019.
- [2] A. Fantoni, “Dispositivos wearable para o campo da saúde: reflexões acerca do monitoramento de dados do corpo humano,” *Temática*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 185–198, 2016.
- [3] L. Piwek, D. A. Ellis, S. Andrews, and A. Joinson, “The rise of consumer health wearables: Promises and barriers,” *PLoS Med*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1–9, 2016, doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001953.
- [4] R. Ferrão, *Wearables: Dispositivos Inteligentes para Saúde e Bem-Estar*. TCC (Graduação) - Curso de Engenharia da Computação, Universidade Virtual do Estado de São Paulo, Franca, 2019.
- [5] J. Lee and others, “Sustainable wearables: Wearable technology for enhancing the quality of human life,” *Sustainability*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 466, 2016, doi: 10.3390/su8050466.
- [6] F. Sabry, T. Eltaras, W. Labda, K. Alzoubi, and Q. Malluhi, “Machine learning for healthcare wearable devices: The big picture,” *J Healthc Eng*, pp. 1–25, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/4653923.
- [7] OMS (Organização Mundial da Saúde), “Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs),” 2021.
- [8] OMS (Organização Mundial da Saúde), “UN NCD Taskforce & the WHO Special Programme on Primary Health Care, Awards 2022.....NOW CLOSED,” 2022.

- [9] IBGE (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística), “Em 2019, Expectativa de Vida era de 76,6 anos: Agência de Notícias,” 2020.
- [10] G. da Silva, J. Bald, A. Bonetti, and C. da Silva, “Prevalência de infecção do trato urinário em idosos assistidos por um programa de medicina preventiva em Cascavel/PR,” *FAG Journal of Health (FJH)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 352–356, 2020.
- [11] T. Stuart *et al.*, “Context-aware electromagnetic design for continuously wearable biosymbiotic devices,” *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 228, p. 115218, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.bios.2023.115218.
- [12] K. H. C. Massa, Y. A. O. Duarte, and A. D. P. Chiavegatto Filho, “Análise da prevalência de doenças cardiovasculares e fatores associados em idosos, 2000-2010,” *Cien Saude Colet*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 105–114, 2019, doi: 10.1590/1413-81232018241.02072017.
- [13] E. A. F. Nilson, A. B. Metzler, M.-E. Labonté, and P. C. Jaime, “We are modelling the effect of compliance with WHO salt recommendations on cardiovascular disease mortality and costs in Brazil,” *PLoS One*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 1–15, 2020, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0235514.
- [14] NHS, “Cardiovascular disease.”
- [15] M. B. Shishehgarhaneh, A. Keivani, R. C. Moehler, N. Jelodari, and S. R. Laleh, “Internet of things (IoT), building information modeling (BIM), and digital twin (DT) in construction industry: A review, bibliometric, and network analysis,” *Buildings*, vol. 12, no. 10, 2022.
- [16] S. Greengard, *The internet of things*. MIT Press, 2021.
- [17] N. Surantha, P. Atmaja, David, and M. Wicaksono, “A review of wearable internet-of-things device for healthcare,” *Procedia Comput Sci*, vol. 179, pp. 936–943, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.083.
- [18] A. Javdan, J. Smith, and E. Brown, “Wearable IoT-enabled health monitoring system,” *EURASIP J Wirel Commun Netw*, vol. 2023, pp. 1–15, 2023.
- [19] M. Poongodi and others, “Recent Advances on IoT-Assisted Wearable Sensor Systems for Healthcare Monitoring,” *Biosensors (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 10, p. 372, 2019.
- [20] H. Banitaba, L. Zhang, and X. Wang, “IoT and IoMT in Healthcare: Real-time Communication and Remote Monitoring,” *J Med Syst*, vol. 47, pp. 1–12, 2023.
- [21] P. Nandi, K. R. Anupama, A. Bajaj, S. Shukla, T. Musale, and S. Kachadiya, “Performance evaluation of machine learning algorithms on System on Chips in wearables for healthcare monitoring,” *Procedia Comput Sci*, vol. 218, pp. 2755–2766, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2023.01.247.
- [22] D. Verma *et al.*, “Internet of things (IoT) in nano-integrated wearable biosensor devices for healthcare applications,” *Biosens Bioelectron X*, vol. 11, p. 100153, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.biosx.2022.100153.
- [23] A. Arumugam and others, “Does Google Fit provide valid energy expenditure measurements of functional tasks compared to those of Fibion accelerometer in healthy individuals?,” *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, vol. 15, no. 6, p. 102301, 2021.
- [24] T. Hong, Z. Wang, X. Luo, and W. Zhang, “State-of-the-art research and applications of machine learning in the building life cycle,” *Energy Build*, vol. 212, p. 109831, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.109831.
- [25] J. Xie *et al.*, “A survey of machine learning techniques applied to software defined networking (sdn): Research issues and challenges,” *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 393–430, 2019.
- [26] S. Sah, “Machine learning: A review of learning types,” 2020.

- [27] C. Cortes and V. Vapnik, "Machine learning," *Springer Science and Business Media LLC*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 273–297, 1995, doi: 10.1023/a:1022627411411.
- [28] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016, pp. 785–794. doi: 10.1145/2939672.2939785.
- [29] R. Dulari and R. Nehra, "Decision tree algorithm for data science," *J Emerg Technol Innov Res*, pp. 87–91, 2021.
- [30] C. Zhang and Y. Ma, *Ensemble machine learning: Methods and applications*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [31] A. Bhandari, "Guide to AUC ROC Curve in Machine Learning: What is specificity?," 2024.

